

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

**SUstainable Management of soil Organic Matter to
Mitigate Tradeoffs between C sequestration and nitrous
oxide, methane and nitrate losses**

Deliverable D5.4

**Application of the Σommit index to fruit orchards:
background, methods and results of the application of
the Σommit index on fruit tree orchards.**

Due date of deliverable: M54

Actual submission date: 31.07.2024

Acronym: ΣOMMIT

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2021

Project duration: 36 Months

Topic: CM8

Project type: Medium-sized project

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DELIVERABLE NUMBER: D-WP 5.4

DELIVERABLE TITLE Application of the Σommit index to fruit orchards: background, methods and results of the application of the Σommit index on fruit tree orchards.

DELIVERABLE TYPE: Technical report

WORK PACKAGE N: WP5

WORK PACKAGE TITLE: Tradeoffs and synergies synthesis: best practices, critical thresholds, indicators

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List of Abbreviation

Abbreviation	Description
C	Carbon
N	Nitrogen
Δ SOC	Soil organic carbon changes
GHG	Greenhouse gases
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NO ₃ ⁻ N	Nitrate nitrogen
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
Σ i	Σ ommit index
T-Ocs	Tade-off components

1. Introduction

In previous deliverables D5.2 and D5.3, we introduced the final version of the SOMMIT index, a composite indicator designed to identify optimal agricultural management strategies by balancing trade-offs among soil organic carbon changes (Δ SOC), nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions, nitrate nitrogen (NO_3-N) leaching, and crop yield. This index utilizes fuzzy logic, a rigorous mathematical framework that, unlike the binary and rigid nature of Boolean logic, accommodates the concept of partial truth. This flexibility makes it well-suited for capturing the complexities of agricultural systems, which are characterized by intricate interdependencies among multiple interacting factors (Amini et al., 2020a; Zrobek et al., 2020), and for managing the uncertainties and subjectivities involved in interpreting and evaluating such complex systems, enabling a more holistic representation of sustainability's multiple dimensions. Additionally, fuzzy logic allows for dynamic adjustments in evaluation criteria to cater to the varying priorities and perspectives of users and permits the incorporation of expert knowledge, which may enhance the robustness and effectiveness of the evaluations.

Four alternative versions of the SOMMIT index have been developed, reflecting the perspectives of different stakeholders with distinct economic, productivity, and sustainability priorities. So far, we have applied the SOMMIT index to evaluate annual crops.

In this deliverable, we present the application of the fuzzy-based trade-off analysis index to evaluate and compare three different management strategies in an orchard setting.

Fruit tree ecosystems are significant carbon pools, accounted for in annual national greenhouse gases (GHG) reports (IPCC, 2006), and their production is crucial for long-term food security on a global scale (FAO, 2018). The fruit sector is highly competitive, and yield is a significant concern for fruit growers. At the same time, the internal quality standards and consumer expectations, especially for those sold in the fresh market, are very high (Codron et al., 2005). These productive pressures have led to massive agricultural intensification in orchards over the last century, increasing production through high inputs of inorganic fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides (Reganold et al., 2001). However, this intensification has also led to increased production costs and environmental damage within and around the orchards (Reganold et al., 2001).

These concerns have spurred interest in environmentally friendly production methods, such as organic management, conservation practices, and integrated pest management techniques (Dib et al., 2016; Simon et al., 2010). Agricultural practices like minimized soil disturbance and permanent soil cover may positively impact biodiversity and ecosystem services (Palm et al., 2014). In particular, there is a growing body of research exploring the introduction of selected weeds as cover plants with specific functional ecological traits and agronomical characteristics as one possible strategy for managing weeds in orchards with minimal herbicide use. Reintroducing biological diversity in orchard systems through cover crops could enhance biological regulation, contribute to controlling bio-aggressors in the agroecosystem, reduce the use of chemicals, and provide additional services such as benefiting pollinators, reducing runoff and soil erosion, and supporting natural enemies of crop pests (Barberi et al., 2018). The challenge lies in promoting a weed community that supports biodiversity while minimizing competition with crops (Mézière et al., 2015).

In this study, the Σ OMMIT index was applied to data from a newly planted experimental organic apricot orchard in Central Italy to compare three agrobiodiversity management strategies: soil ripping versus reduced tillage at orchard planting, soil tillage versus minimum/no tillage, and the introduction of different weed communities as cover crops. The experiment compared three management systems: Business as Usual (BAU), a tilled organic management system;

Innovative Tilled Diversified System with Cover Crops and Compost Use (ICC); and Innovative Diversified System with Minimum Tillage, Natural Cover, and Compost Use (INC).

The application of the ΣI provided a comprehensive evaluation of the three management strategies, highlighting the trade-offs between agroecological intensification practices and their impact on GHG emission and productivity.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Environmental conditions

The data analysed in this study derive from the “MAIntenance of Organic oRchards” long-term experiment (MAIOR LTE) conducted by CREA - Research Centre for Olive, Fruit and Citrus Crops - located in Rome, Italy (latitude 41.8000 N, longitude 12.5690 E, altitude 86 m a.s.l.).

The site climate is classified as hot-summer Mediterranean (Köppen classification), characterized by mild winters and warm to hot summers. Long-term weather data (1971–2000) identify January as the coldest month (7.5 °C), and July and August as the warmest (25.1 and 25.4°C, respectively) and driest months. November and December are the wettest months (average rainfall of 110–120 mm month⁻¹).

Monthly weather data during the experiment were collected using an automatic weather station (Campbell Scientific, Inc.) located within the experimental site. From 2016 to 2018, temperatures during winter were close to 0°C, peaking around 35°C in summer. The period from 2019 to 2021 showed warmer winters and milder summers. Summer rainfall was very low in 2016, 2017, and 2019, while autumn 2016, winter 2018, and 2020 experienced higher precipitation than the 5-years average, with an extreme event in November 2019 (270 mm).

The soil at the experimental site is classified as Eutric Phaeozem (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015), with a sandy clay loam texture (22% clay and 25% silt). It has a mean bulk density of 1.4 g cm⁻³, an electrical conductivity of 0.140 mS cm⁻¹, and a pH of 7.0. It contains 1.22 g kg⁻¹ of N and 20.1 g kg⁻¹ of organic matter (0–40 cm layer).

2.2. Experimental design

The MAIOR LTE started in winter 2017, following a participatory process that engaged farmers in identifying key factors to include in the research activities (Ciaccia et al., 2019b). The area designated for the LTE had not been cultivated for over 10 years and was regularly mowed twice per year, in autumn and spring. The design of the MAIOR LTE is a split-plot arrangement with three blocks. The main plot was allocated to organic agronomic management, comparing three systems with varying levels of agroecological intensification, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Description of the three agroecological strategies compared in the LTE

Experiment ID	Description
BAU - Business As Usual	Local practices commonly used for organic fruit orchards: soil tillage and organic commercial fertilizer (24% of organic C and 5% of organic N on dry basis).
ICC - Innovative diversified system with Cover crops and Compost	Soil tillage and Municipal Waste Compost (MWC - 37% of organic Carbon and 2.8% of organic N content on dry basis) supplied by the “AMA Roma Spa” company, deriving from organic wastes collected in the metropolitan area of Rome. Cover crops (mixture of <i>Phacelia sp.</i> and <i>Coriandrum sativum</i> in tree inter-rows + mixture of <i>Trisetum sp.</i> , <i>Vicia sp.</i> and <i>Trifolium sp.</i> on tree rows).
INC - Innovative diversified system with Natural cover and Compost	Soil tillage limited to transplanting furrow and soil ripping in central inter-row space, natural cover, MCW.

Two self-compatible cultivars of apricot (*Prunus armeniaca* L.) with varying vigour levels were selected for the study: Kioto* (KM), a medium-ripening cultivar (3rd week of June in Central Italy) characterized by moderate vigour and high productivity, and Pieve* (PM), a medium-late ripening cultivar (4th week of June in Central Italy) known for its high vigour and good productivity. Both cultivars were grafted onto the Myrobalan 29 C rootstock, a clonal selection of *Prunus cerasifera*, which is known for its ability to moderate plant vigour and suitability for a wide range of soil types. The trees were planted at a spacing of 4.4 by 3 m, with each tree occupying an area of 13.2 m². Each sub-plot consisted of 3 rows of 4 trees, covering an area of 132 m².

Figure 1. Pictures from the experimental site showing the apricot tree rows and inter-rows.

2.3. Management practices

The soil was strip-tilled to a depth of 50 cm using a ripper with a 4.4 m spacing, corresponding to the row distance at planting, in mid-March 2017. After two weeks, an additional central ripping was carried out for tree planting in the INC treatment, while the entire soil surface was tilled to a depth of 15 cm in the BAU and ICC treatments. A transplant furrow was then prepared in all systems along the previously ripped rows.

A drip irrigation system was implemented, delivering approximately 1500 m³ ha⁻¹ from June to September, with irrigation occurring twice a week for 12 hours each time.

Fertilizers were applied at planting and then annually in autumn, starting from October 2017, coinciding with soil operations (milling to a depth of 10 cm in BAU and ICC, and strip milling – 0.5 m wide – for compost incorporation near the apricot trees in INC) and the sowing of Agroecological Service Crops (ASC) in ICC. Two ASCs mixes (Table 2) were sown in autumn and then mowed and chopped in late spring following a strip system. Ground covers, both natural and introduced, were mowed twice per year, in spring and autumn, coinciding with fertilizer application.

Table 2. Description of the agroecological service crops sowed in the Innovative diversified system with Cover crops and Compost (ICC) management system.

ACS ID	Description	Species
Mix 1	Species with nutritional and competitive functions against spontaneous flora, sowed in the inter-row spaces.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - italian ryegrass - <i>Lolium multiflorum</i> (60% of pure dose standard, 35 kg ha⁻¹) - white mustard - <i>Sinapis alba</i> (40%, 2.5 kg ha⁻¹) - white clover - <i>Trifolium repens</i> (40%, 5 kg ha⁻¹) in 2017–2018 - <i>Avena sativa</i> (60%, 84 kg ha⁻¹) since autumn 2019 - <i>Vicia sativa</i> (40%, 44 kg ha⁻¹) since autumn 2019
Mix 2	Flower strip sowed in the central area (1.4 m-wide) during the whole experiment, with attractive function for beneficial insects.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - purple tansy - <i>Phacelia tanacetifolia</i> (90%, 9 kg ha⁻¹) - coriander - <i>Coriandrum sativum</i> (20%, 4 kg ha⁻¹) - <i>Borago officinalis</i> (20% 0.4 kg ha⁻¹)

2.4. Data collection and elaboration

Since fall 2021, fluxes of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O, have been measured together with weather parameters and inorganic N availability along the tree rows and in the inter-row space. NO₃ availability has been used as proxy for N leaching.

The N₂O and NO₃ data were normalized according to the area occupied by rows and inter-rows space, by multiplying the values measured on the rows by 0.8 and those measured in the inter-row space by 1.2. The two values were then averaged. N₂O emissions data were subsequently converted into CO₂ equivalents, using a conversion factor of 298 (N₂O Global Warming Potential). SOC variation data were obtained by averaging the difference in SOC between each year and the previous one, starting from 2017 and continuing until 2022.

Yield data from 2022, mean N₂O emissions, and NO₃ leaching for 2021-2022, and ΔSOC data for the period 2017-2021 were used as input for the fuzzy-logic-based trade-off analysis. The data were first normalized between 0 and 1, then processed through the three phases of the fuzzy logic aggregation process: fuzzification, minimum inference engine, and defuzzification, as detailed in chapter 2.3 of deliverables D5.2 and D5.3. This process aggregates the four trade-off

components into a composite index, the Σ omit index, which ranges from 0 (very bad) to 1 (very good), scoring the overall sustainability of the system based on the trade-off associated.

Four different versions of the Σ_i were developed, each reflecting a distinct narrative. These narratives describe different groups of potential stakeholders, each with distinct perspectives, needs, and sustainability visions. Each narrative is characterized by a unique set of weighting schemes, each composed by 18 aggregation rules, reflecting the different importance assigned to the four trade-off components (T-Ocs) during aggregation process, as detailed in Table 3. For a comprehensive description of the narratives and the weight assignments, please refer to Chapter 2.4 of deliverables D5.2 and D5.3. All analyses were performed using the R Studio environment.

Table 3. trend of the mean weights assigned to the four T-Ocs in narratives V1 a group of young innovative farmers (Young farmers), V2 a multinational agrochemical company (Agrochem corporation), and V3 an EU national agency responsible for allocating Common Agricultural Policy subsidies to farmers (CAP paying agency), compared to the balanced version (V0), where T-Ocs were weighted 25 each.

Σ_i version	Δ SOC	N ₂ O emissions	NO ₃ -N leaching	Crop yield
V0	25	25	25	25
V1	≈	↓	↓	↑
V2	↓	↓	≈	↑
V3	↑	≈	≈	↓

3. Results and discussions

Figure 2 illustrates the trend of the four analyzed trade-off components across the three agroecological strategies: BAU (Business As Usual), ICC (Innovative Diversified System with Cover Crops and Compost), and INC (Innovative Diversified System with Natural Cover and Compost).

- N₂O emissions:** The BAU system exhibited the highest N₂O emissions (~3.3 Mg CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹ y⁻¹). In contrast, ICC and INC systems showed lower emissions, N₂O emissions: In contrast, ICC and INC systems showed lower emissions, suggesting that cover crops and compost, by increasing organic matter, may improve soil structure and soil aeration, thereby reducing anaerobic conditions that promote N₂O production. Additionally, cover crops potentially take up residual soil nitrogen, reducing its conversion to N₂O. Minimal tillage in the INC system also likely reduced soil disturbance, which may have further lowered N₂O emissions.
- NO₃-N leaching:** The INC system had the highest NO₃ content (~12 kg ha⁻¹ y⁻¹), followed by BAU and ICC. This suggests that a combination of natural and planted cover crops might reduce N leaching more effectively than traditional management, though natural cover crops alone may be less effective.
- SOC change:** All three systems recorded an increase in SOC, with BAU showing the lowest increase. The INC system had the highest SOC gains (~0.8 Mg ha⁻¹ y⁻¹), followed by ICC, indicating that cover crops might enhance soil carbon sequestration through added organic matter.
- Crop yield:** The BAU system achieved the highest crop yield (~3 Mg ha⁻¹), while ICC and INC produced lower yields. This trade-off suggests a potential challenge in balancing high yields with environmental sustainability, as cover crops might compete with trees for nutrients and water. Furthermore,

municipal waste compost, which is used in ICC and INC, has a lower nitrogen percentage compared to the commercial organic fertilizer applied in BAU. This may result in a lower N supply to the plants, negatively impacting overall tree nutrition and final yield.

Figure 2. Trade-off components trend across three agroecological strategies: BAU (Business As Usual), ICC (Innovative diversified system with Cover crops and Compost), INC (Innovative diversified system with Natural cover and Compost)

Figure 3 presents the median and interquartile ranges of the Σ omit index (Σ_i) values obtained by applying the trade-off analysis for version 1 (V1 - young farmers), version 2 (V2 - agrochemical corporation), and version 3 (V3 - CAP paying agency) across the three agroecological systems (BAU, ICC, and INC) under examination. Version 0, which assigns equal weight to the four trade-off components, is marked by black stars and serves as the reference.

Under the balanced scenario (V0), ICC and INC achieved the highest Σ_i values, suggesting that these systems offer a more sustainable solution when all trade-off components are considered equally.

In the *young farmers* narrative (V1), ICC received a lower Σ_i distribution median, indicating it was evaluated as less sustainable. Similarly, INC's Σ_i distribution median was almost equal to the V0 Σ_i value but was entirely left-skewed, suggesting this system was also scored as less sustainable. BAU, on the other hand, had a Σ_i distribution median more consistent with V0, indicated by a narrower interquartile range, which signals higher agreement among the 18 aggregation rules of this weighting scheme. This outcome likely stems from the higher weight given to system productivity over environmental impact in this narrative, as seen in table 3. Consequently, the lower yields from ICC and INC most likely caused their lower evaluations.

The CAP paying agency narrative (V3) showed an opposite pattern, where ICC and INC reached Σ_i distribution medians very close to the balanced scenario (V0), with a narrow interquartile range. Conversely, BAU had a significantly lower Σ_i distribution median. This narrative assigns higher importance to environmental impact, particularly soil organic carbon increase, and less relevance to yield (table 3). Consequently, systems that enhance environmental sustainability, such as ICC and INC, are favoured.

The agrochemical corporation narrative (V2) exhibited an intermediate pattern. The Σ_i distribution median values for BAU, ICC, and INC almost overlapped with the V0 version, though all distributions were strongly left-skewed. This suggests that under this narrative, system productivity and environmental impact are balanced in their importance but that, in general, the evaluation was stricter, resulting in a higher occurrence of lower scores for all three agroecological systems.

Figure 3: Median and interquartile ranges of the Σ_{ommit} index (Σ_i) value distributions for version 1 (young farmers), version 2 (agrochemical corporation), and version 3 (CAP paying agency) across three agronomic systems: BAU (Business As Usual), ICC (Innovative Diversified System with Cover Crops and Compost), and INC (Innovative Diversified System with Natural Cover and Compost). Black stars indicate the Σ_i in a balanced scenario (version 0) where equal weight is given to all trade-off components.

4. Conclusions

In this deliverable, we present the results of a Σ_{ommit} trade-off analysis conducted on an apricot orchard in central Italy, comparing three management systems with increasing levels of agroecological intensification: BAU (Business As Usual), ICC (Innovative Diversified System with Cover Crops and Compost), and INC (Innovative Diversified System with Natural Cover and Compost).

The findings indicate that systems with reduced soil disturbance and the introduction of cover crops, using municipal waste compost as the sole fertilizer (ICC and INC), were characterized by increased SOC gain and overall reduced N fluxes. However, their productivity was lower compared to the more traditional system (BAU).

Four alternative variants of the Σommit index were applied, each reflecting different evaluation criteria related to distinct stakeholder categories. In all four Σi variants, the ICC agroecological system emerged as the most sustainable management strategy, although with fluctuation among the Σi variants, as it received a lower score distribution in the young *farmers* narrative, where higher priority is given to system productivity and less to environmental impact.

These results confirm that the introduction of cover crops, especially a mix of planted and spontaneous ones, increased overall system sustainability, resulting in a positive trade-off between the reduction in crop yield, the net gain in SOC, and the reduced N losses.

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